

Quantitative Treatment of the Variation of Ionic Activity and Equivalent Conductivity of Solutions of Strong Electrolytes with Dilution

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By modifying Debye-Hückel theory, as discussed in a previous paper, equation for the mean activity coefficient of an ion in solutions of strong electrolytes of the uni-bivalent type has been deduced. The equation has been subjected to test using available data on BaCl₂ and K₂SO₄ and has been found satisfactory.

Equations for the equivalent conductivity of solution of strong electrolytes of 1 : 1 and 2 : 1 types have also been deduced and subjected to test using the data available in the literature on KBr, NaCl, HCl and CaCl₂ and have been found satisfactory.

The equations can be expressed in the same cube root form as that of Ghosh.

In a previous publication^{1†} it has been pointed out that the activity coefficient of the ions should be taken into consideration in applying Boltzmann formula to the distribution of the ions in the ion atmosphere of the central positive ion in the Debye-Hückel theory^{2,3}. The introduction of the mean activity coefficient of the ions in the Boltzmann formula leads to a modification of the expression for χ (Kappa). For a uni-univalent electrolyte the modification consists in replacing $(\Sigma n)^{1/2}$ by $(\Sigma n)^{1/2}/(2\pi a)^{1/2}$ where a represents the "effective diameter" of the ions concerned and n the number per cc of an ionic species.

In this paper following the same line of argument as has been recorded in the previous paper¹, equation for the mean activity coefficient of the ions of unsymmetrical strong electrolytes in solution has been deduced and subjected to test using the data on BaCl₂ and K₂SO₄.

Equations, for the equivalent conductivity of 1 : 1 and 2 : 1 electrolytes in solution, have also been deduced and subjected to test using the data available in the literature on KBr, NaCl, HCl and CaCl₂ solutions.

Derivation of the equations :

(a) Equation for the mean activity coefficient : The Debye-Hückel^{2,3} equation for the mean activity coefficient f of a strong electrolyte dissociating into v_+ and v_- ions having valencies z_+ and z_- may be written as follows :

$$-\log f = \frac{N e^2}{4.606 DRT} \left[\frac{v_+ z_+^2 + v_- z_-^2}{v_+ + v_-} \right] \chi \quad \dots (1)$$

where $\chi = \left[\frac{4\pi e^2 \Sigma n_i z_i^2}{DkT} \right]^{1/2}$

† Errata—Paper¹, last page, last para:—Please read $e/2L^2(2\pi a)\chi$ instead of $e/L^2(2\pi a)\chi$, $2L^2(2\pi a)$ instead of $L^2(2\pi a)$ and $0.96e/2L^2(2\pi a)$ instead of $0.96e/L^2(2\pi a)$.

Let us assume that the bivalent ion in the 2 : 1 electrolyte is positively charged and n its number per cc of the solution. Then the number of univalent negative ions per cc of the solution is $2n$.

By applying Boltzmann distribution law, taking into consideration the mean activity coefficient of the ions, we may write

$$(n_+ f) dv = n f_0 \exp(-2e\psi/kT) dv \quad \dots (2)$$

$$(2n_- f) dv = 2n f_0 \exp(e\psi/kT) dv \quad \dots (2a)$$

where ψ is the potential due to the central positive ion at a distance r from it, dv a small element of volume surrounding a point in this region, and $(n_+ f)$ and $(2n_- f)$ represent respectively the activity of the positive and negative ions in the solution at a sufficient distance from the central positive ion, so that $\psi=0$.

Then the density of charge ρ is given by the following expression :

$$\rho = [2en_+ - 2en_-] = [-2enf_0/f] [3e\psi/kT - \frac{2}{3}(e\psi/kT)^2 + \dots] \quad \dots (3)$$

Assuming, as has been done by Debye and Hückel, that terms in $(e\psi/kT)^2$ and higher order terms are very small and can be neglected compared to $(3e\psi/kT)$ we may write

$$\rho = -(2enf_0/f)(3e\psi/kT) \quad \dots (3a)$$

Hence the expression for χ should be written as follows

$$\chi = \left[\frac{12\pi e^2(2n) f_0}{DkT} \frac{1}{f} \right]^{1/2} \quad \dots (4)$$

According to Donnan's theory⁴ of membrane equilibria $(n_+ f_0)(2n_- f_0)^2 = (n_+ f)(2n_- f)^2 = 4(n^1)^2(f)^2$ where $(n^1)^2 = (n_+)(n_-)^2$

Therefore, $4(n)^2(f_0)^2 = 4(n^1)^2(f)^2$, or $(f_0/f) = \left(\frac{n^1}{n}\right)$

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It is to be noted that $n^1 \gg n$ and n^1/n may be looked upon as the ratio of the negative charge density close to the central positive ion to that in the bulk of the solution.

Substituting the aforesaid value of f_0/f in equation (4) it may be written as follows :

$$\chi = \left[\frac{12 \pi e^2 (2n)}{DkT} \frac{n^1}{n} \right]^{1/2} \dots (5)$$

Let L be the average distance between two neighbouring ions, then as one molecule contains three ions, so :

$$L = \left(\frac{1}{3n} \right)^{1/3} \text{ or } (3n)^{1/3} = \left(\frac{1}{L} \right)^{1/3}$$

Now putting $L = 2\pi a x$ where a is the "effective ionic diameter", π has its usual value and x a dimensionless variable and substituting $1/(2\pi a x)^{1/3}$ for $(3n)^{1/3}$ in equation (5) we may write :

$$\chi = \left[\frac{8\pi e^2}{DkT} \frac{(n^1/n)}{2\pi a x} \right]^{1/2} [3n]^{1/3} \dots (5a)$$

It has been shown in a previous paper^{1†} that $\left(\frac{n^1/n}{x} \right)$ remains constant and close to unity over a certain range of values of n . Therefore, over that range of values of n , the following equation should hold good :

$$\chi = 1.414 \left[\frac{2e^2}{DkTa} \right]^{1/2} [3n]^{1/3} \dots (5b)$$

This point will be considered again in the discussion.

Substituting the aforesaid value of χ in equation (1) and putting $NC/1000$ for n it may be written for a 2 : 1 electrolyte as follows :

$$-\log f = \frac{Ne^2}{4.606 DRT} (2 \times 1.414) \left(\frac{2e^2}{DkTa} \right)^{1/2} \left(\frac{3N}{1000} \right)^{1/3} (C)^{1/3} \dots (6)$$

$$= 2.83 [B_0/(A)^{1/3}] (C)^{1/3} \dots (6a)$$

where $A \times 10^{-8} \text{ cm} = a$ and B_0 represents the other constants in equation (6). At 0° , $B_0 = 0.687$.

A plot of $-\log f$ against $(C)^{1/3}$ has been found to be linear, as it should be according to equation (6a) since all the other terms are constant, but the straight line cuts the $(C)^{1/3}$ axis at a point $(C_0)^{1/3}$ which is above zero. This means that when C becomes C_0 , f becomes unity. Therefore, equation (6a) has to be used as

$$-\log f = 2.83 [B_0/(A)^{1/3}] [(C)^{1/3} - (C_0)^{1/3}] \dots (6b)$$

$$= 2.83 [0.687/(A)^{1/3}] [(C)^{1/3} - (C_0)^{1/3}] \dots (6c)$$

(b) Equations for equivalent conductance : The Debye-Hückel-Onsager limiting law⁵ for the equivalent conductance of an electrolyte solution may be

† It may be noted that both (n^1/n) and x decrease as n increases, so it is quite reasonable to assume that their ratio $\left[\text{i.e. } \frac{n^1/n}{x} \right]$ may remain constant over a certain range of values of n .

written as follows :

$$\lambda = \lambda_0 - [A_1 \lambda_0 + A_2] \chi \dots (7)$$

$$= \lambda_0 - mB \sqrt{C} \dots (7a)$$

where λ represents the equivalent conductance of the electrolyte at concentration C and λ_0 the constant equivalent conductance reached at a sufficiently high dilution, A_1 and A_2 are constants which can be calculated from theory. In equation (7a) $m = (A_1 \lambda_0 + A_2)$ and $B \sqrt{C} = \chi$. For a uni-univalent electrolyte at 25° , $A_1 B = 0.23$, $A_2 B = 60.65$ and $B = 0.3291 \times 10^8$.

It follows from what has been discussed already that χ of the Debye-Hückel^{2,3} theory has to be modified and the modified χ , [vide 5a], should be expressed as

$$\chi = \frac{G}{\sqrt{A}} [(C)^{1/3} - (C_0)^{1/3}] \dots (8)$$

where $A \times 10^{-8} \text{ cm} = a$ and $G = 0.4024 \times 10^8$ for a 1 : 1 electrolyte and for a 2 : 1 electrolyte $G = 1.414 (0.4607 \times 10^8)$ at 25° .

Substituting the aforesaid modified value of χ in place of $B \sqrt{C}$ in equation (7a), it is to be written as follows :

$$\lambda = \lambda_0 - \frac{mG}{\sqrt{A}} [(C)^{1/3} - (C_0)^{1/3}] \dots (9)$$

$$= \lambda_g - m_1 (C)^{1/3} \dots (9a)$$

where $\lambda_g = \left[\lambda_0 + \frac{mG}{\sqrt{A}} (C_0)^{1/3} \right]$ and $m_1 = \frac{mG}{\sqrt{A}}$...

λ_g and m_1 are to be treated as characteristic constants of the linear equation (9a).

Equation (9a) may also be written as

$$\ln(\lambda/\lambda_g) = \left[1 - m_2 \left(\frac{1}{V} \right)^{1/3} \right] \dots (9b)$$

$$\text{or } \ln(\lambda_g/\lambda) = m_2 \left(\frac{1}{V} \right)^{1/3} \dots (9c)$$

when $m_2 \left(\frac{1}{V} \right)^{1/3}$ is very small compared to unity.

In equation (9c) m_2 is a constant and V is the volume in liter containing a gram molecule of the electrolyte.

It is to be noted that equation (9c) is of the same form as that deduced by Ghosh⁶.

Processing of data and verification of the equations :

(i) On mean activity coefficient : Equation (6b) has been subjected to test using data from freezing point measurements collected from "The electrochemistry of solutions" by Glasstone⁷. The data are recorded in Table 1, in column 1 of which are mentioned the electrolyte and the equation used, the values of the constants in the equation and the values of the crystallographic radius r_+ and r_- of the positive and negative ions and also that of A "the effective ionic diameter". In the table obs. f and cal. f represent the observed and calculated mean activity coefficient and C represents molal concentration. Upto $0.1N$ no distinction has been

made in this paper between a molal and molar concentration.

(ii) *On equivalent conductance*: The equation (9a) has been subjected to test using the data recorded in the Tables 2-5 where C represents the concentration of the electrolyte in moles per liter. In column 1 of the Tables under the head miscellaneous are recorded the values of λ_g and m_1 of equation (9a) and also the values of A, ν_+ and ν_- .

The data recorded in Table 2 have been collected from the book "Electrolyte solutions" by Robinson and Stokes⁶ and (F-O), (S) and (R-S), denote the equations of Fuos and Onsager, Shedlovsky and Robinson and Stokes, used for calculating λ . All these equations contain two empirical constants either λ_0 and a or λ_0 and b and Shedlovsky's equation is an empirical one.

In the Tables 3 and 4 are recorded the data on NaCl and CaCl₂ collected from Robinson and Stokes Book, (LL) denotes Onsager's limiting law used for the calculation of λ .

In Table 5 are recorded the data collected from Shedlovsky's paper⁸.

Discussion

It will be noticed from the data recorded in Table 1 that the agreement between the values of f observed and those calculated by using equation (6b) is satisfactory within the concentration range 0.0005M to 0.1M for both the electrolytes K₂SO₄ and BaCl₂. At 0.1M of BaCl₂ the calculated value of f is about 2.6 per cent lower than that observed. It may be taken as an indication that equation (6b) is just beginning to fail from this concentration.

The data recorded in Table 2 show that the values of λ calculated by using equation (9a) agree with those observed within ± 0.035 per cent. The other three equations fit the experimental data very well. However, the values of λ_0 used in these equations differ from one another appreciably. Obviously λ_0 for KBr has got a definite value and if that value differs appreciably from those used in the equations then the agreement between the observed and calculated values will not be so good as it now appears from Table 2. It is to be noted that since λ_0 and a vary from equation to equation, they should be treated as characteristic constants of the equation used and not of KBr.

In Table 3 the data enclosed within bracket have been collected from Shedlovsky's paper⁸. In Onsager's limiting law represented by equation (7a), there is only one empirical constant λ_0 and the other (mB) can be calculated from theory and herein lies its special merit. The Onsager limiting law, however, agrees with the experimental values of λ of the NaCl solutions up to 0.002M. After that deviation becomes quite marked. Robinson and Stokes⁶ equation fits the experimental data better than equation (9a) up to 0.005M but after that there is not much difference between that equation and equation (9a).

It will be seen from the data on solutions of CaCl₂ recorded in Table 4 that the agreement between the values of λ observed and calculated by using equation (9a) is better than those calculated by using Robinson and Stokes equation⁶.

The data recorded in Table 5 show that the values of λ of the HCl solutions calculated by using equation (9a) agree well with those observed.

It is to be noted that equation (9a) holds good so long as C is greater than C₀.

The value of A, found for the BaCl₂ solutions and recorded in Table 1, is 8.2 Å. It may be noted that it is nearly 2.6 times the sum of the ionic radius of the Ba and Cl⁻ ions.

The value of ν_- recorded in Table 1 for the K₂SO₄ solutions is that of the S ion. It will be noticed that A for K₂SO₄ is found to be 5.4 Å and (5.4-1.33) is close to (4.8-0.74) where 0.74 Å is the ionic radius of the Zn ion. It is, therefore, probable that the radius of the hydrated SO₄ ion is close to 4.0 Å.

The values of A recorded in the Tables 2 and 3 for the solutions of KBr and NaCl are 6.0 Å and 5.52 Å and they are 1.83 times and 2 times the sum of the ionic radius of K⁺ and Br⁻ and of Na⁺ and Cl⁻ respectively.

The value of A for CaCl₂ recorded in Table 4 is, like that found for BaCl₂, 2.6 times the sum of the ionic radius of the Ca and Cl⁻ ions.

The value of A for HCl recorded in Table 5 is 5.7 Å. The value of A found from freezing point data and recorded in a previous publication¹ is about 7.3 Å. The difference between 7.3 and 5.7 is 1.6 Å and it is quite close to the diameter of the oxygen atom 1.48 Å. Therefore, the low value of A for HCl found from conductivity data may be attributed to the peculiar mechanism of conduction of current in water by the H⁺ ion which is believed to gain by the diameter of the oxygen atom in the process.

Since, A is always larger than the sum of the Pauling radii of the positive and negative ions, so it is to be concluded that the ions are hydrated⁶.

It is evident from the data recorded in the Tables 1-5 that the observed values of f and λ agree well with those calculated by using the equations (6b) and (9a) respectively. This agreement over a fairly wide range of concentration may be taken as a proof of the validity of the assumption underlying equation (5b) from which the equations (6b) and (9a) follow. Further justification of the assumption that $\left(\frac{n^+}{x}\right)$ remains constant and close to unity over a certain range of values of n may be provided in the following way. It follows from what has been discussed already that the volume of the cell containing a molecule of the 2:1 electrolyte is 3(L)⁸. Let us take the bivalent ion as positively

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF MEAN ACTIVITY COEFFICIENT WITH DILUTION

Miscellaneous	C	0.0005	0.001	0.005	0.01	0.05	0.1
BaCl ₂							
Eqn. (6b)							
2.83 B ₀ /(A) ^{1/2} =0.68, obs. f.		0.89	0.865	0.77	0.72	0.568	0.501
(A)=8.2 Å	Cal. f.	0.892	0.863	0.772	0.721	0.567	0.488
(C ₀) ^{1/2} =0.006							
γ ₊ =1.35 Å γ ₋ =1.81 Å,							
K ₂ SO ₄	C	0.0005	0.001	0.005	0.01	0.05	0.1
Eqn. (6b)							
2.83 B ₀ /(A) ^{1/2} =0.84, Obs f.		0.885	0.85	0.75	0.69	0.505	0.421
(A)=5.4 Å	Cal. f.	0.886	0.852	0.742	0.682	0.507	0.421
(C ₀) ^{1/2} =0.017,							
γ ₊ =1.33, γ ₋ =1.84,							
A for ZnSO ₄ =4.80 Å							

TABLE 2—VARIATION OF λ OF KBr WITH C AT 25°

Miscellaneous	C × 10 ⁴	λ Observed	Values of λ calculated from			
Eqn. (9a)			(F-O)	*(S)	*(R-S)	(9a)
λ _g =153.61	13.949	149.27	148.27	148.26	149.26	148.24
m ₁ =48	27.881	146.91	146.91	146.92	146.92	146.86
A=6.0 Å	42.183	145.88	145.89	145.89	145.90	145.86
γ ₊ =1.33,	59.269	144.90	144.91	144.90	144.91	144.93
γ ₋ =1.95,	71.696	144.30	144.30	144.28	144.29	144.35
(γ ₊ +γ ₋)=3.28 Å			λ ₀ =151.75, λ ₀ =151.68	λ ₀ =151.67		
			a=3.6 Å b=91	a=3.2 Å		

* Shedlov-ky's equation (S)

$$\lambda = \lambda_0 - (A_1 \lambda_0 + A_2) B \sqrt{C} + bC(1 - A_1 B \sqrt{C})$$

TABLE 3—VARIATION OF λ OF NaCl WITH C AT 25°

Miscellaneous	C	λ Observed	Values of λ calculated from		
Eqn. (9a)			(LL)	(R-S)	(9a)
λ _g =128.41	0.0005	124.51	124.45	124.51	124.71
m ₁ =46.6	0.001	123.74	123.63	123.75	123.75
A=5.52 Å	0.002	122.66	122.46	122.63	122.54
γ ₊ =0.95 Å	0.005	120.64	120.14	120.68	120.44
γ ₋ =1.81 Å	0.01	118.53	117.53	118.57	118.38
	0.02	115.76	113.83	115.81	115.76
	0.05	111.06		111.03	111.23
	0.1	106.74		106.52	106.78
			λ ₀ =126.45, λ ₀ =123.45		
			a=4 Å		

charged, then the average density d₁, of negative charge contributed by the two negative ions is 2e/(L)²(3). Now if ²L²(2πa) is the volume surrounding the central positive ion then since 2πa is quite large (a > 7.0 Å) this volume will also very probably

TABLE 4—VARIATION OF λ OF CaCl₂ WITH C AT 25°

Miscellaneous	C	λ Observed	λ calculated from		
Eqn. (9a)			(LL)	(S)	Eqn. (9a)
λ _g =198.78	0.00025	181.90	181.88	182.02	182.04
m ₁ =107	0.0005	180.32	180.23	180.52	180.28
A=7.4 Å	0.001	128.20	127.91	128.47	128.08
γ ₊ =0.99,	0.0015	126.61	126.12	126.95	126.53
γ ₋ =1.81	0.0025	124.23	123.29	124.65	124.26
(γ ₊ +γ ₋)=2.80 Å	0.0035	122.47	120.99	122.85	122.54
	0.005	120.36	—	120.69	120.48
	0.01	115.65	—	115.65	115.74
			λ ₀ =135.85, λ ₀ =135.85		

TABLE 5—VARIATION OF λ OF HCl WITH C AT 25°

Miscellaneous	C	λ Observed	λ calculated eqn. (9a)
Eqn. (9a)	0.0005	422.62	422.90
	0.001	421.24	421.21
λ _g =429.41	0.002	419.27	419.03
m ₁ =82	0.005	415.68	415.39
A=5.7 Å	0.01	411.88	411.75
	0.02	407.12	407.16
	0.05	398.97	399.20
	0.1	391.20	391.35

contain both the negative ions inside it*. Therefore, the average density d₂ of negative charge in this volume element is 2e/L² (2πa)(3). For reasons stated already we may put

$$n^1/n = d_2/d_1 \quad \dots (10)$$

Then it follows from equation (10) that

$$n^1/n = d_2/d_1 = L/(2\pi a) = x \quad \dots (10a)$$

Therefore $\left(\frac{n^1/n}{x}\right) = 1$ and consequently $\left[\frac{n^1/n}{x}\right]^{1/2}$

= 1. It may be noted that even if $\left(\frac{n^1/n}{x}\right)$ is slightly less than unity, $\left(\frac{n^1/n}{x}\right)^{1/2}$ will be closer to unity.

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* This can be verified from a consideration of the magnitudes of $\frac{1}{x}$ (double layer thickness) $2\pi a$ and L ; noting that $\frac{1}{x}$ is less than L .